

Technology in Training Delivery of Education Management: AI in ELT Approach

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this research is to describe availability of tablet computers, personal computers, mobile devices and the other technologies offers such as using virtual reality, augmented reality and artificial intelligence can be used in practical English classroom in good strategies for lecturers and to share the knowledge with their students or some trainers. The research employed a descriptive qualitative method on with the communicative approach collaborating AI in ELT. The results show that technology can take offer several existing jobs and could create opportunities which offer new ways to learn, communicate, share, create and collaborate with human beings. Using these technologies, training design and understanding human being preferences are important steps in seeing on technology in training such as e-learning: online training, simulations and games and mobile learning. Computers can be trained to accomplish specific tasks by processing large amounts of data and recognizing patterns in the data. In classroom that can be used technology as digital tools for the implications for language classroom. It can be improve the learning with using four skills (reading, listening, speaking, writing) using AI for English language teaching. Here are some recommendations for teachers and lecturers to use the technology and to improve teaching method in English classroom. These technologies as smart machines that think like human with the ability to stimulate intelligence through a process by using computers, smartphones etc. such as Kuki, Elsa, Quillionz, Readlang and many more AI will help students.

KEYWORDS: AI in ELT, Education Management, Technology.

INTRODUCTION

Technology in education management can refer to some technological tools in English learning of education management. Digital platforms to manage all of support teaching and learning as improve whole efficiency within the education sector (Lai & Bower, 2019; Junaidi et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2019). The training designs and the important steps in capitalizing on technology in training such as e-learning: online training, simulations and games and mobile learning (Vlasova et al., 2018; Barakhsanova et al., 2017; Andini et al., 2022).

Electronic learning systems (Electronic learning or E-learning) can be defined as a form of information technology applied in the field of education in the form of a website that can be accessed anywhere.

Bullen & Jeans (2007: 176) defines e-learning as a learning process that uses internet technology to facilitate, deliver, and enable distance learning processes to take place. The concept of learning is actually not new. E-learning has started in the 1970s (Waller and Wilson, 2001). Various other terms used include: online learning, internet-based learning, virtual learning, web-based distance education, e-learning, web-based teaching and learning.

The term artificial intelligence (AI) may appear in 1956 at the Dartmouth conference. However, actually the concept of artificial intelligence has been discussed long before that. Researchers have carried out follow-up research to develop this artificial intelligence. Around 1900, several philosophers appeared who issued mathematical theories that could become the basis for computer machines or artificial intelligence (Hamet & Tremblay, 2017; Müller & Bostrom). These philosophers were G. Boole, A. N. Whitehead and Russell. In the 1930s, A. Turing, C. Shannon, and J.V. Neumann discussed how computers can represent knowledge, and stated that computer machines would only move if data had been entered (Bournez et al., 2020; Webb, 2019). Some researchers debate how to get that data into the machine so that the machine can learn. Moreover, the world already had digital computers in the 1950s. After World War II, the first computers appeared in 1946's. Entering the 1950s, John McCarthy, Marvin Lee Minsky, Herbert Alexander Simon, Allen Newell, and Edward Albert Feigenbaum emerged who began to formulate the term AI. Ai first appeared in 1956 at a meeting in Dartmouth. The 1980s is also known as the second wave of AI. The following are some of the researchers who contributed to this era, namely David Rumelhart, Lotfi Zadeh, John Holland, Lawrence Fogel, Ingo

Rechenberg and John Koza (Seising & Tabacchi, 2013; Aldo et al., 2022). The third development of AI began in the 2000s when computers and the internet already existed. Its development products include the invention of the World Wide Web or WWW by Tim Berners-Lee in 1989, cloud systems which started in 1950 and continued to be developed until the 1990s, the emergence of the term big data by John R. Mashey in 1998, and deep learning by Geoffrey Hinton in 2006. Artificial intelligence (AI) in training has been learnt. Artificial intelligence has numerous potential benefits for education, which could improve the working lives of teachers and the learning journeys of students. AI can provide as a wide-ranging branch of computer science concerned with building smart machines capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence (Kuleto et al., 2021; Renz & Hilbig, 2020; Anderson, 2019). English language teaching (ELT) can be considered the educational aim in terms of improving the potential of students that can be interacted. Using these technologies, computers can be trained to accomplish specific tasks by processing large amounts of data and recognizing data. AI can be played a critical function both students and lecturers of English classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Communicative Language

The Communicative Approach or communicative language teaching is there can be as an approach to language in teaching in the classroom with interactive way between teacher and student that can be emphasizing both the means and what you want to study (Mo'minova & Mo'minova, 2017). In targeting teachers choose classroom activities must be having communicative abilities for students (Thamarana, 2017). That basic can be promoting the collaboration through technology using AI.

Communicating Value approach by Kotler's theory (1991) is the communications process consists of nine elements: sender, receiver, message, media, encoding, decoding, response, feedback, and noise. To get improving every students making a good practices with their new friends into AI (Ng & Chu, 2021).

Internet Services approach based on client or server technology. Using the tools as a control what are you doing on it with the client applications on their computers such as web browser software of AI in ELT.

B. AI (Artificial Intelligence)

In this increasingly advanced era, AI (Artificial Intelligence) has become a hot topic to be asked and discussed. In a variety of sectors, AI has proven its potential to transform the way we live and work. AI is a technology designed to make computer systems capable of imitating human intellectual abilities. It enables computers to learn from experience, identify patterns, make decisions, and complete complex tasks quickly and efficiently (Maechem, 2020; Bhaskar et al., 2022).

C. ELT Growth Through Technology

With the spread and development of English throughout the world, English is used as a second language in some countries and there are also some people use English as a first language, and that is a high prestige in this country. At present the role and status of English in India is higher than before as evidenced by its position as a major subject of teaching media, curricula as the number of English learners increases different teaching methods have been applied to test the effectiveness of the teaching process.

English language teaching has been in the everyday setting for many years and it's significance continues to grow, driven, in part, by the Internet. Graddol's research (2000) describes that in 2000 there were around one billion English learners, but a decade later the number had doubled. This shows a surge in learning English, which peaked in 2010. Furthermore, it was found that more than 80% of the information stored on the internet was in English, so there are more Non-Native than Native language users and the diversity of contexts in terms of learners, ages, nationalities, learning backgrounds and so on has become the hallmark of ELT today. With the rapid development of science and technology, the emergence and development of multimedia technology and its application to teaching, featuring audio, visual and animation effects play a full role in English classroom teaching and set a favorable platform for reform and exploration of English teaching models in new era (Bakhromovich, 2022; Ismail et al., 2010) It is proved that multimedia technology plays a positive role in promoting students' activities and initiatives and teaching effect in English class. Furthermore, technological innovation has gone hand in hand with the growth of the English language and changed the way we communicate and learn, just like English.

D. Kuki, ELSA, Quillionz, Readlang

Kuki is small pieces of data sent from a website and stored on a user's computer by a web browser when the user is opening a web page. It is designed to be a reliable mechanism for websites to remember information about a state (such as products added to a cart

in an online store) or to record a user's surfing activity (including clicking certain buttons, logging in, or recording the number of pages visited) (Hakim & Rima, 2022). It is also used to remember pieces of information entered by users into text fields, such as names, addresses, credit card numbers and passwords (Skrebeca et al., 2021). It perform important functions, such as the role as authentication Kuki which is used by web servers to know if a user is logged in and which account is used.

The next smart application namely ELSA (English Learning Speech Assistant) Speaking, one of the top 5 AI English training companies in the world by research sniper by Forbes, has launched an AI-enabled API (Application Programming Interface) in its features.

System-wise, the workings of this API will be integrated directly with learning technology from ELSA partners which aims to develop English performance through speech recognition and interactive teaching methods. The achievement of Artificial Intelligence ELSA technology in the ELSA Speak application has been used by more than 20 million users worldwide (Kholis, 2021; Samad & Aminullah, 2019). As English communication is rapidly evolving into a modern skill requirement, it is important for Edtech and educational Companies to incorporate this competency into their curricula. Students want digital training and quality learning in a practical way, anytime, anywhere (Samad & Ismail, 2020; Anggraini, 2022).

Quillionz (the teacher creates questions from the reading text) creates a variety of questions on the content, including multiple choice questions, memorization questions and short descriptive questions. Once the questions are ready, it allows its users to create and refine them as many times as needed. Furthermore, it generates editable notes from your content, using its AI capabilities (Vachev et al., 2022; Sharookhan et al., 2022).

The last is the Google Chrome browser using the ReadLang extension. The ReadLang extension is an application that is quite unique because it uses the repetition method which is considered suitable for learning foreign languages. In order to use this application, one must first visit a site that contains long articles in the language one wants to learn (Falcón, 2022; Magfirah et al., 2022). After that the ReadLang application will save the article, next, the ReadLang app will then translate the article and repeat the translation of certain words or phrases so it can be remember it quickly. That way this application is perfect for someone or students who also want to master a few phrases in a foreign language.

METHODOLOGY

This researcher used descriptive qualitative method with the communicative approach collaborating AI in ELT to find out CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) with AI in ELT. This makes it possible to combine those approaches are using cellular systems and internet access to use AI. Here is showing the pictures to you how to act in the classroom AI in ELT such as forming a group with three or four classmates using AI in ELT. Compare the capabilities into Apple's iPhone with smartphone, there are a lot of features on the applications with different qualities of AI. Every tools have beneficial and weakness on them, it is depends on human beings in using the application.

Figure 1. Communicative approach collaborating AI in ELT

The figure above shows that AI in ELT is part of a management method for teaching English which in its application provides the benefits of learning English in a fun way, there is feedback between the teacher and students which is able to increase student productivity by operating applications that help improve speaking as well as reading, Furthermore, technologies that can be used such as quest AI, Invideo AI, ChatGPT AI, and others.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Artificial Intelligence in English Language Teaching

Artificial intelligence technology has a technology can be seen how machines that mimic human intelligence to perform tasks and can iteratively improve themselves based on the information they collect. The experiments using AI for speaking class, I may not see AI can change off for the lecturer but I may see it in a good way to give the students more creatively when using KUKI AI (Kuki is built using AIML (Artificial Intelligence Markup Language) which makes it an intelligent chat-bots for fun purposes). Kuki is an award-winning AI brain designed to entertain humans. The application can be working on chat-bots that can be practicing those vocabularies with chit-chat, voice chat, AI reading. Quizzes, and games in English just for fun, improving vocabulary and expressions while the students can be using it. Artificial intelligence can be shown new way for teaching and learning approaches that are now undergoing testing in different contexts (Russell, 2010). AI can be able to assess using theirs thought and your point of level that you have assessed by humans. Using the technology as a good potential in that way to provide the students in speaking practice for students. The machines learning have long been on the core speech recognition in voice instruction automation and tailored pronunciation training (Timms, 2016). Elsa apps is one of good English pronunciation app, speak English in short fun dialogues, get instant feedback from proprietary artificial intelligence technology. Powered by Artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms, quillionz is a platform that lets you build a host of quality quizzes and assessments within seconds and completely free. Readlang is a web-app and chrome extension that helps the reader learn by translating web sites and creating flashcards and word list. Artificial intelligence technologies can be given by the students with personalized one-to-one tutoring (Dixon-Román et al. 2020). By using these applications can be innovative language-learning services can be given more effective and affordable with combining on machine learning and traditional language-learning techniques. Here are some information about twenty four of digital tools for formative assessment:

1. Animoto – Gives students the ability to make a short, 30-second share video of what they learned in a given lesson.
2. Ableton -music production, creation, and performance
3. Crowd signal – Quick and easy way to create online polls, quizzes, and questions. Students can use smartphones, tablets, and computers to provide their answers, and information can be culled for reports.
4. Diigo -social bookmarking website that allows signed-up users to bookmark and tag Web pages. Additionally, it allows users to highlight any part of a webpage and attach sticky notes to specific highlights or to a whole page
5. Edpuzzle - Allows teachers to create and/or import videos and embed questions to check for understanding
6. Flipgrid – This tool has been recently updated. Students can use 15-second to 5-minute videos to respond to prompts; teachers and peers can provide feedback. GDPR compliance: You must select “Student ID # list” forthe grid type and create custom IDs for each student manually to use Flipgrid. You cannot create public grids, even if password protected.
7. Google Forms – A Google Drive app that allows you to create documents those students can collaborate on in real time using smartphones, tablets, and laptops.
8. Kahoot – A game-based classroom response system, where teachers can create quizzes using internet content.
9. Kaizena – An online tool for providing students with real-time feedback on their digitally-uploaded work. Teachers can highlight or speak to give verbal feedback and attach teacher-created, reusable resources to student work.
10. Nearpod – This tool is nice in that you can not only gather evidence of student learning, like an all-student response system, but you can also create differentiated lessons based on the data you collected.The basic version (30 students or less) is free.
11. Noteflight - online music writing application that lets you create, view, print and hear professional quality music notation right in your web browser
12. Padlet - From your hobby to your career, your class notes to your final exam, your mood board to your runway show, padlets can help you organize your life. GDPR: Cannot ask students to create accounts and must ensure submissions provide no identifiable data.

13. Peergrade – A platform that allows teachers to create assignments and upload rubrics. Students upload work and are anonymously assigned peer work to review according to the rubric.
14. Piktochart - Create beautiful info graphics, flyers, posters, presentations and reports easily with absolutely no design experience.
15. Pinterest -social media platform which people use to search, save and learn different things through visual images (check out How Schools Are Using Pinterest to Educate)
16. Poll Everywhere – Teachers can create a feedback poll or ask questions. Students respond in various ways, and teachers see the results in real-time. With opened questions, you can capture data and spin up tag clouds to aggregate response. There is a limit to the number of users.
17. Quizlet – Create flashcards, tests, quizzes, and study games that are engaging and accessible online and via a mobile device.
18. Miro - online collaboration and white boarding platform for teams and organizations of all sizes
19. Seesaw – This tool helps teachers improve parent communication and makes formative assessment easy, while students can use the platform to document their learning.
20. Sketch Up - 3D modeling computer program for a wide range of drawing applications such as architectural, interior design, landscape architecture, civil and mechanical engineering, film and video game design
21. Spark post – This app from Adobe allows teachers to add graphics and visuals to exit tickets.
22. Survey Monkey – Teachers can create and deliver online polls and surveys. (Note... this is an app that requires a monthly fee, but may be worth the cost depending on your polling or survey needs.)
23. Twist - keeps all your conversations organized by topic in asynchronous threads - so your team can choose when to connect to discuss meaningful topics. GDPR compliances - Delete your Twist team at the end of the course.
24. Youtube – video making and curating potential

Figure 2. Home screen Kuki app

An online AI chat bot named Kuki was created to interact with people in the metaverse. Go to this website: @kuki_ai, register and create a username and password. Enter account. You can see like these pictures in the link, then you can chat with Cookies and use the features.

Chatbot Kuki has natural language processing and artificial intelligence, or AI, to understand what is being said. In response to questions about what happened, the chatbot can provide information about the sky, ceilings, etc.

Figure 3. AI Kuki Chatbot Display

Users can ask the chatbot about Cookie capabilities if interested. The chatbot will introduce and provide all the information needed, possibly entertaining for hours with the chatbot's many features. Weather predictions for any city can be requested via the chatbot. Go beyond normal typing to ask with Kuki AI. This tool also offers features that will help to ask questions more easily than other AI tools. Cookie AI chat-bots have a voice chat feature where it can talk with AI personalities and still get natural conversations, so if it wants to speak English easily and more effectively, this really helps the user's English speaking training and also the user can ask questions some unknown English vocabulary.

CONCLUSION

AI technology cannot only bring convenience to human life. It is important to highlight the integration of AI in English Teaching not to replace human instruction but to enhance the person to person experience. In using this app, it is not only used personally, but can also be applied with anyone such as friends, family or co-workers. In this study the use of AI Cookies in learning English and of course this can be used in the classroom.

In this day and age it is very easy to learn about anything including learning languages, because artificial intelligence, humans are very helpful and make lives easier. Learning English nowadays is not difficult, starting from speaking, writing and reading we can learn it easily as explained in this study.

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